

TWITTER SENTIMENT ANALYSIS ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ONE DATA INDONESIA WITH SEMI SUPERVISED SVM

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Data is a new source of wealth. Data sovereignty must be realized immediately (Presiden RI, 2019). The quality data is a reference for policy formulation, especially in planning, monitoring and evaluating programs. The use of quality data in policy formulation is very useful to achieve the targets properly so the development goals can be achieved effectively (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2010). Data quality plays an important role in the preparation of national-level work plans to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Sekretariat Nasional Open Government Indonesia, 2020).

Quality is a form of measurement of the extent to which a set of characteristics inherent in an object meets the requirements. In statistical organization, the objects are statistical output, statistical process, institutional environment, and statistical system. The quality of statistical output is very influential in the quality management framework because all components lead to statistical output (United Nations, 2019). To obtain quality and easily accessible data, the Indonesian government is improving data governance through the implementation of One Data Indonesia. One Data Indonesia (ODI) is a government data management policy to support development planning, implementation, evaluation, and control (Peraturan Presiden No.39 Tahun 2019 Tentang Satu Data Indonesia, 2019).

The implementation of ODI needs to notice the principle of One Data Indonesia. Data generated by data producers must meet data standards, have metadata, meet data interoperability rules, and use reference codes and/or master data. With ODI, it is hoped that any data published through the ODI portal can be used freely, in an open format, and can be used and redistributed by anyone without conditions other than citing the source and data owner (Peraturan Presiden No.39 Tahun 2019 Tentang Satu Data Indonesia, 2019). Thus, the use of government data is not only limited to internal use between agencies, but also as a form of fulfilling public data needs for the community (Indrajit, 2018).

The tangible implementation of ODI started in 2017 (Media Indonesia, 2016). This was conveyed by the Minister of National Development Planning that the use of one data was started for program

planning for the 2017 fiscal year. The implementation of one data in Indonesia was started to be applied by ministries/agencies by integrating the data into one comprehensive data.

In its implementation, ODI still faces obstacles and challenges, such as inconsistent and scattered data in various public institutions with difficult access, lack of coordination between data-owning institutions, and non-standardized data. Important components that must be maximized in the implementation of ODI are strengthening data management and governance, publication and dissemination of open data through portals, as well as involvement and sustainability of data users (Islami, 2021). As one of the main components in ODI, the opinion of data users on the implementation of ODI is important to be researched. One of the data sources that can be used to analyze opinions is Twitter data. Twitter provides services to its users to read and write opinions. In addition, Twitter users in Indonesia are also quite widespread. By the 191.4 million Indonesians who actively use social media, 63.6% of them use Twitter (Global Digital Insights, 2021).

Sentiments contained in the opinions of Twitter users can be analyzed into useful information. Sentiment is the center of various communication studies where negativity and polarization have a significant influence on economic conditions, social life, politics, to development issues that are integrated with information technology. The dynamics of interaction between social media users is considered representative so that it becomes important data to be analyzed as development recommendations (Singgalen, 2021).

Sentiment analysis is a computational study of people's opinions, feelings, emotions, and attitudes towards an entity such as products, services, issues, events, topics, and attributes. Sentiment analysis is one of the most active studies currently in the study of natural language processing, data mining, information retrieval, and web mining (Antonio et al., 2017). Sentiment analysis can be a more effective and cost-effective alternative to surveys (Wei et al., 2021).

Sentiment analysis with machine learning is divided into 3 categories, they are unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and supervised learning. The three approaches have their respective advantages. The advantages of unsupervised learning include saving time and money because there is no need to labeled the data. Supervised learning requires more energy to label the data, but the model that is formed usually has better performance than other methods (Ligthart et al., 2021).

The semi-supervised learning expected to reduce the shortcomings of the two previous approaches by collaborating them. Semi-supervised learning uses unlabeled data supplemented by labeled data to form a classification model. Semi-supervised learning is commonly used for sentiment analysis with large amounts of unlabeled data. This model produces quite good results when the dataset is very large (Ligthart et al., 2021). Semi-supervised learning is popularly applied to sentiment analysis of Twitter data with a lot of unlabeled data (Da Silva et al., 2016). Based on the data held by the researcher, the semi-supervised learning is considered to be the most suitable for this research.

Currently, semi-supervised learning has been developed. Several semi-supervised learning based on research by Jamshid Bagherzadeh in 2018 include self-training methods, generative methods, co-training methods, margin-based methods, graph-based methods, and semi-supervised boosting. Pseudo-labeling is a technique in self-training that can be applied to both labeled and unlabeled data (Fudholi and Juwairi, 2009). Yulan He and Deyu Zhou mentioned that the self-training with

pseudo-labeling is a simple, robust, and does not need to focus too much on tuning parameters (He and Zhou, 2011). In addition, Lee Dong-Hyun in his research mentions that the pseudo-labeling method is a simple and efficient method (Dong-Hyun Lee, 2013).

Pseudo-labeling techniques can be used in machine learning methods such as Naïve-Bayes, Neural Network, etc. Lighthart et al. in 2021 compared three machine learning, namely Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naïve Bayes, and Random Forest with a self-training. Naïve Bayes produces the best accuracy with the highest accuracy of 94%. Then Chandani et al. do a comparison between SVM, Naïve Bayes and Artificial Neural Network where SVM produces the best accuracy (Chandani et al., 2015). Furthermore, Ipmawati et al. perform comparisons between SVM, Naïve Bayes and K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN). In this study SVM also produced the best accuracy compared to the other two algorithms (Ipmawati et al., 2017).

This research was begun with data collection. Data were obtained by scraping data from January 1, 2017 to December 31, 2021 using the library “Twint” based on 8 keywords. The keyword is determined by researchers based on words that have a relationship with One Data Indonesia. The data collection results 21,286 unique data with detailed data can be seen in **Table 1**.

Table 1. The results of scraping Twitter data.

Keyword	Total
@datagoid	1,311
data terbuka	7,622
data.go.id	136
integrasi data	948
manajemen data	3,406
pengelolaan data	3,170
data governance	927
satu data Indonesia	3,855
Total	21,286

Data from Twitter is then labeled manually. Tweets are classified into positive (1), negative (-1) and neutral (0). Positive and negative labels are given to their tendency towards SDI implementation. While the neutral label is given to tweets that do not show a positive or negative trend, such as tweets containing information, notifications, and tweets that are not related to the implementation of one data Indonesian, such as tweets about internships, webinars, etc. There is 2,778 data used in manual labeling which can be categorized in 323 in positive, 2,153 in neutral, and 302 in negative. Data from manual labeling categorized in 2,778 data with positive categories as many as 323, neutral 2,153, negative 302. Then the text preprocessing to remove noise in the data.

Classification with a semi-supervised applied by technique pseudo-labeling. The method used is SVM with 5-fold cross validation. In each modeling, weighting is done with TF-IDF and resampling with SMOTE. The modeling in this study was carried out 2 times. Data is divided into several sets as seen in **Table 2**.

Table 2. The distribution of dataset for modeling.

Dataset Name	Amount of Data
Labeled data	2,729
Unlabeled Data I (25%)	4,076
Unlabeled Data II (75%)	12,227
Total	19,032

The first modeling is applied to manually labeled data. The data is divided into 3 data sets, namely training, testing, and validation. The model is formed with training and predictions are made on data testing and validation. Resampling is only done on training data. First model produces an average accuracy of 0.937931 with a standard deviation 0.008062. The model is used to make predictions on 25% of the non-labeled data. Prediction results are presented in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Prediction results 25% of unlabeled data in first modeling.

The classification results are assessed using a confusion matrix to see the model's performance in classifying tweet data. The first model produces an accuracy value obtained by testing the model with data validation of 82.03% data testing of 80.67%. The accuracy value is quite consistent, indicating that the first model is quite good at classifying. Based on the **Figure 2**, it can be concluded that the model predicts well for the neutral category and quite well for the positive and negative categories.

Figure 2. Modeling Precision, Recall, and F1-Score of the first modeling.

The second modeling is applied to the combined data of training data and predicted data from the first model. The modeling is done using the same technique as the first modeling. The second model produces an average accuracy of 0.916902 with a standard deviation of 0.011869. The model is used to make predictions on 75% of the unlabeled data. Prediction results are presented in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Prediction results 25% of unlabeled data in second modeling.

The second model produces an accuracy value of 79.70% for testing with data validation and 82.25% with data testing. The accuracy value in the second model is also quite consistent which shows that the second model is also quite good at classifying. Based on the **Figure 4**, it can be concluded that the model can predict well in the neutral category and quite well for the positive and neutral categories. Furthermore, the model tends to be better at predicting the positive and negative categories, but slightly worse for the neutral category.

Figure 4. Modeling Precision, Recall, and F1-Score of the second modeling.

In this research, the researchers also make a comparison of the performance of semi-supervised learning techniques pseudo-labeling on Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naïve Bayes (NB) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithms to see how well our methods in clasifying the tweets. The performance to be compared is the result of cross validation and the accuracy value. First comparison was made for model 1 using data labeled as training data. Based on the cross validation shown in **Figure 5**, SVM has the highest accuracy value followed by Naïve Bayes, and K-Nearest Neighbors. Based on the **Figure 6**, it can be seen that SVM has the lowest standard deviation value. This shows that SVM is the best model in terms of cross validation.

Figure 5. Comparison of cross validation in first modeling.

Figure 6. Comparison of the standard deviation in first modeling.

The next comparison is carried out in second modeling, where the training data used is a combination of the training data used in first modeling and pseudo-labeled data (predicted data from first modeling). Based on the cross validation shown in **Figure 7**, SVM has the highest accuracy value followed by NB and KNN. Based on **Figure 8**, it can be seen that SVM has the lowest standard deviation value. Furthermore, KNN has a standard deviation of accuracy that is not much different from SVM then followed by NB with the highest standard deviation of accuracy. Based on modeling2, SVM still produces the best model in terms of cross validation.

Figure 7. Comparison of cross validation in second modeling.

Figure 8. Comparison of the standard deviation in second modeling.

The first comparison was made for first modeling using data labeled as training data. Based on the **Figure 9**, it can be concluded that SVM has the best accuracy in first modeling compared to the other two algorithms. While KNN has the lowest accuracy and NB is slightly better.

Figure 9. Comparison of accuracy in first modeling.

Furthermore, second modeling is carried out using training data in the form of a combination of training data for first modeling with pseudo-labeled. Prior to modeling, resampling was also carried out in the second modeling. Based on **Figure 10**, it can be concluded that SVM has the best accuracy in first modeling compared to the other two algorithms. While KNN has the lowest accuracy and NB is almost close to SVM.

Figure 10. Comparison of accuracy in second modeling.

The results of the sentiment classification show that the sentiments of Twitter users regarding the implementation of One Data Indonesia tend to be positive and neutral. Positive sentiments of Twitter users tend to be related to systems, integration, government and governance. Meanwhile, on the negative sentiment, some Twitter users also discussed systems, governance, and government. This shows the lack of stability in the system, governance, and government so that different sentiments emerge.

The word that tends to be used a lot in positive sentiment is the word "integration". This shows that the opinion of Twitter users regarding integration in Indonesia tends to be positive. While the word that tends to be used a lot in negative sentiments is "valid". This indicates that Twitter users' sentiment towards data validity in Indonesia tends to be bad.

Sentiment classification of tweets using the SVM algorithm results in an accuracy testing data of 80.67%. Then the classification with semi-supervised SVM produces an accuracy of 82.25%. The increase in accuracy indicates that the addition of pseudo-labeled can improve accuracy. In addition, semi-supervised SVM proved to have better performance than semi-supervised Naïve Bayes, and semi-supervised K-Nearest Neighbor.

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